

INFORMATION ON TOPONIM (ORONIM) PLACE NAMES, DENOV DISTRICT

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Abstract: This is it in Denov district in the article there is was calm down and their species, distributed regions, their meanings about data given Learned data on the basis of district settlements schedule given.

Key words: Oronyms, classification, oronymy object, patamonims, mountain, hill, gorge.

Some geographical names place geographical place, that of place, geographical of the object to himself special from the features appear will be Such names between plains: (Greek, oros - " mountain ") - mountains, hills, valleys, hills, gorges, ravines and another orographic of objects names This type of names relief shape and of the elements to himself special features expression is enough Specialists according to toponyms another types relatively calm down less studied.

Peaceful of objects names much steady and long lifetime own names save stay with differs. Time pass with geographical object relief change possible, however that's it relief expression who does name preserved will remain. For example, the meaning of a cliff or a hill stated geographical of names some of them present at the time that's it place relief exactly does not mean can Also note that All right geographical in objects that it was such as oronymic of objects names semantics among them clear didn't happen names less it's not. And this addition toponymic requires research [1].

Denov and Golden districts within the limit is located from the gorges one's name It is called **surprising**. To be called such saba gorge wide stretched out and gorge steep cliffs between and tall embers out stands Here visit ordered a person directly this nature from the scenery to surprise falls This is the reason if need so is the name placed says local peoples.

In the territory of the district of the boysun mountain range one comb has been **Kyzilkurgan** mountain located of the mountain to get such a name main reason his soils and the rock of stones reddish in the shade is that With that together fortress i.e people like is the location. That's it of the mountain southeast in the part **Doors** a narrow gorge there is. This is a gorge Kyzilkurgan

mountain From the Boysun mountain range separate stands i.e the door task performs.

of the district western in the part Boisun mountain range in the skirts is located from the mountains one's name **Nuragan** is called It 's really cool external forces i.e the wind and water in effect a lot places eaten away and light fell stones let's see possible [3].

Big Besmel mountains - Uzun, Denov district Bobotog of the ridge on the south-western slope , in the north Argamchi and in the south Faizova cliffs between located Big Besmel mountains translation in doing partially translation done and it complete translation Let's do "*Katta Borli*". *mountain* said the meaning means The highest place 1292 m. Main heights 900–1100 m. Little Besmel of Mt the most tall place 1196 m. From the south-west to the northeast direction, length 16 km. Bobotog ridge with transversely they catch Big Besmel mountains chalk of the era sandstone, limestone, siltstone, conglomerate, gypsum from rocks, water part of the Paleogene hard from limestone Created . That's why for the mountains bullet part to a vertical view have Mountains strong broken, dry cliff and streams a lot occurs. In the skirts Argamchi and Faizova cliffs at the bottom less debit springs available of water salinity 1-2 grams per liter. Water tank northeast in the part less fragmented nakedness occurs. Simple and full gray soils light mechanic content. Some in places indigenous rocks over opened the rest because of soil in general no. Get on your side gray soils spread out in places color, brown, color, wormwood plants, green gray in soils wormwood with together pistachios grows [5].

Bobotog of the ridge around one how much hills there is to be so from the hills one **Koltepa** is called Hill around one how much lakes there is to be These are lakes spring in the season precipitation during small streams that's it to the lakes water they pour In the summer dry remains.

G' ajirkhan from Mt in the northeast is located tall to the hill **Koktoba** is called Here *blue+red* from his words fruit was To the blue height relative to given if so, *sorry* this is the word tepa dialect pronunciation.

Table 1

In the territory of the district there is has been calm down and their group

No	Calm down name	Calm down type
1	Sangardak	Mountain; gorge
2	Bobotog	Mountain range
3	Xayrondara	Urochisa

4	Eshiklari	Dara
5	Katta Besmel tog'i	Mountain
6	Sho'rdara	Dara
7	Oktumshuk	Hill
8	Toshlok	Dara
9	Teshiktepa	Hill
10	Supa	Adir
11	Kurgontepa	Hill
12	Okjar	Cliff
13	Koktoba	Hill
14	Nuragan	Hill
15	Ko'ltepa	Hill

Table the author by was built

Bobotog ridge between one how much cliffs is located is so from the cliffs one's name **White** . The cliff is minerally white soil area from rocks content found That's why white for earthen ravine, local population in the language compact , Akjar shape received

Snout bulging obvious apparently standing place That is hill or of the cliff around obvious to the eye thrown away On the slopes don't push traces saved . On the surface cliff and there are karst cavities. Chalk, gray, white-yellow limestone and from clay organize found hill **Flowing** is called With the same name in the district named There is also a village.

Ancient fortress of the ruin instead height - called "**Kurgontepa**". With the same name in the district named hill there is.

Top part flat was hill It is called **Supa**. With a name like that named hills Boysun mountain range and Bobotog on the slopes of the ridge a lot occurs .

In the district of villages from the names one **Hole**. Village mountain range in the area located We know it 's raining a lot rain because of floods coming cases mountainous in the regions very many occurs. Of the village to get such a name come, hills between piercing pass as a result one how much holes appear did In this area living population in the language of the phrase "**Toshiktoba**". to the body to come reason will be

Big Besmil from the mountains the south in the west located narrow pass road It is called **stone**. Stone of being called reason caste process because of from the mountains eaten away small stones with is covered.

Two sides mountain range with wrapped long stretched population address **Valley**. These are the places a person by mastered.

Different mineral types from soils content found to the place **Brine** is called Kyzilkurgan of Mt between is located from the gorges one's name.

Sangardak. With that name named hydronym and there is an oronym. This word is Persian- Tajik from the language received being of the words "sang+gard". addition fruit was Sang-tash, gard-back said the meaning means Translation behind the stone translated as dar will be done. With that name named Syria one in the district how much places there is.

Surkhandarya Uzun, Denov, Schurchi, Kumkurgan, Jarkurgan in the region districts is located **Bobotog** from the north 150 km to the south near stretched. People point of view "*grandfather*" - big , huge , great , holy said the meaning means Mountain the word based on named: great mountain, sacred mountain, eng tall peaked mountain [4]

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